

IOT Solutions for School Bus Transportation

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Abstract: The system presents an Internet of Things (IoT) based smart school bus system to improve the student safety and real-time communication with the parents. Each student uses an RFID card, scanned by a reader at the bus entrance. If authorized, a buzzer beeps, the student's name and status (IN/OUT) are shown on a 20x4 LCD, and a servo motor opens the door. The system also calls the parent using a GSM (SIM900A) module to notify entry or exit. A student counter updates automatically based on boarding status. The bus location is tracked through a GPS module, with real-time latitude and longitude data sent to ThingSpeak cloud. All components, including RFID, GSM, GPS, buzzer, servo and LCD are controlled by an Arduino Uno. The system offers a low-cost, reliable, and scalable solution for safe and smart school transportation.

Keywords: Communication, IoT, Monitoring, School bus, Security, Transportation.

INTRODUCTION

School transportation plays a vital role in ensuring that students travel safely between their home and school. However, managing the student safety, tracking bus location, and informing their parents in real-time remain ongoing challenges. The system introduces a smart school bus system using Internet of IoT technologies to address these needs effectively. The system uses RFID technology to identify the students as they board or leave the bus. When a student scans an RFID card, the system checks authorization, updates their status (IN/OUT), and triggers a buzzer and LCD display. If the student is authorized, a servo motor opens the gate, and a GSM module automatically makes the sending SMS to the parents. A GPS module tracks the real-time location of the bus and sends latitude and longitude data to the ThingSpeak cloud platform. All these components are controlled by an Arduino Uno, creating a cost-effective, real-time monitoring system that enhances the student safety, parental awareness, and overall efficiency in school transportation management.

PROBLEM

In the traditional school transportation systems, there is often no reliable way to verify whether the students have safely boarded or exited the school bus. The parents frequently lack real-time updates about their child's bus status and location, leading to concern and uncertainty. Additionally, manual tracking methods are time-consuming, error-prone, and offer no automated notifications or security features. In emergency cases or unauthorized access, the absence of immediate alerts can compromise student safety. Furthermore, the inability to monitor the bus's real-time location creates difficulties in managing routes and

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responding to delays. Therefore, there is a critical need for an intelligent, automated, and efficient system that can monitor the student boarding status, provide instant notifications to parents, and track the real-time location of the school bus using IoT technologies. Addressing these issues can significantly improve the safety, transparency, and effectiveness of school transportation systems.

APPROACH

The system presents an IoT-based student monitoring system using Arduino Uno, GSM module, RFID, servo motor, LCD, and a buzzer. It is designed to identify the students through RFID card scans and notify their parents via automatic phone calls using the GSM SIM900A module. When the student scan their RFID card, the Arduino processes the data and checks if the card is authorized. If it is valid, the system displays the student's information on the LCD, sounds the buzzer, and triggers the servo motor to open the gate. Simultaneously, the GSM module calls the parent's mobile number to confirm the student's entry or exit. The buzzer alerts when an invalid card is scanned. The system enhances the school bus security and real-time student tracking using the affordable and efficient electronic components.

Figure 1: Circuit Diagram of School Bus Notification System

Figure 2: Circuit Diagram of School Bus Controlled System

Figure 1 is the circuit diagram connection between Arduino Uno and other components such as RFID reader, LCD display (20*4), servo motor, buzzer, and GSM module (SIM900A).

Figure 2 demonstrates the wiring layout for a school bus controlled system powered by the Arduino Uno. The diagram shows the interconnection between key components such as the HC-05 Bluetooth module, L298N motor driver, dual DC motors, and a power source. Commands sent from a mobile device via Bluetooth are interpreted by the Arduino, which then instructs the motor driver to perform directional movements such as forward, reverse, left, or right. The motor driver acts as a bridge between the Arduino and the motors, handling the required current and voltage for motion control. The design enables wireless control of the car using a smartphone interface.

Figure 3 illustrates the circuit connection between the ESP8266 microcontroller and the GPS module, which are used to track and transmit real-time location data to the ThingSpeak cloud platform. The GPS module continuously receives satellite signals and

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provides longitude and latitude coordinates. These coordinates are processed by the ESP8266, which is programmed to connect to a Wi-Fi network and send the data to a specific ThingSpeak channel using its API key. The setup enables remote monitoring of the device's location through any internet-enabled device, offering a reliable IoT-based solution for live GPS tracking.

Figure 3: Circuit Diagram of School Bus Tracking System

Figure 4: Block Diagram of School Bus Notification System

Figure 4 illustrates the block diagram of school bus notification system. In the system, RFID reader (RC255) is an input device and LCD display (20*4), servo, buzzer, and GSM module (SIM900A) are output devices.

Figure 5: Block Diagram of School Bus Controlled System

In Figure 5, the school bus-controlled system is designed to operate using wireless commands. A Bluetooth module (HC-05) is used to receive movement instructions directly from a smartphone application. Once the command is received, it is sent to the Arduino Uno, which acts as the brain of the system. The Arduino processes the instruction and controls the

movement of the car by interacting with the L298N motor driver. The motor driver is connected to DC motors, enabling the car to move forward, backward, or turn left and right depending on the command. The setup allows for real-time remote operation of the car using a mobile device.

Figure 6: Block Diagram of School Bus Tracking System

Figure 6 includes a GPS module to collect the geographical location of the car. The module captures real-time data such as latitude and longitude while the car is in motion. It is also connected to the Arduino board, which reads the coordinates and prepares them for transmission. The data is crucial for live tracking and monitoring of the vehicle’s movement.

To visualize the GPS location data remotely, the system is integrated with ThingSpeak, a cloud-based IoT analytics platform. The Arduino sends the real-time GPS coordinates to ThingSpeak using a network connection (via ESP8266 or GSM). The users can then access the ThingSpeak channel through a web interface or mobile browser to view the location of the car plotted on a map. This allows for continuous location tracking, even from a distance.

Figure 7: Flow Chart of School Bus Notification System

The flow chart of school bus notification system is shown in Figure 7:

- The system becomes active once power is supplied to the microcontroller board.
- It continuously monitors for input from the RFID reader module.
- When a card is scanned, the system reads the unique identifier (UID) from the RFID tag.
- The UID is compared with pre-stored data to check whether the scanned card is registered and valid.
- If the card is recognized as authorized:
 - A confirmation message is displayed on the LCD screen.

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- A buzzer briefly beeps to give audible feedback.
- A servo motor is triggered to open the gate or simulate door access.
- Simultaneously, an SMS is sent to the registered parent's phone number using the GSM module.
- If the card is not authorized:
 - An error or “Unauthorized” message is shown on the LCD.
 - No further actions (like gate control or SMS sending) are performed.
- After processing the current input, the system returns to the initial waiting state and is ready for the next RFID scan.

Figure 8: Flow Chart of School Bus Controlled System

Figure 9: Flow Chart of School Bus Tracking System

Figure 8 is school bus controlled system designed for remote navigation using mobile commands. The flowchart outlines the sequential decision-making process handled by the Arduino microcontroller. Starting from the system initialization, it describes how input commands received via the Bluetooth module and are processed to control motor directions through the L298N driver. The continuous loop ensures responsive movement control until the system is powered off. The flow-based approach simplifies understanding of the system behavior and aids in reliable implementation.

Figure 9 presents a flow-based overview of a GPS location tracking system that utilizes the ESP8266 microcontroller for cloud integration. The flowchart outlines how the ESP8266 continuously reads coordinate data from the GPS module, processes it, and uploads it to the ThingSpeak IoT platform. The logic ensures stable connectivity, error checking, and periodic data transmission for real-time location monitoring. The structured approach supports the reliable data flow and simplifies the cloud-based tracking system implementation.

RESULTS

The implementation of the proposed IoT-based transportation system was successfully divided into three interconnected modules. First, the Bluetooth-controlled car prototype responded accurately to directional commands sent from a mobile application, demonstrating smooth and real-time motion through motor control logic. Secondly, the GPS module, paired with the ESP8266 microcontroller, consistently acquired location data and transmitted it to

the ThingSpeak cloud platform. These updates were reliably visualized via an online dashboard, confirming stable data flow. Lastly, the school bus notification system, equipped with an RFID scanner and GSM module, effectively identified individual students during boarding and sent instant SMS alerts to guardians. The real-time communication not only improves operational efficiency but also significantly enhances the student safety by ensuring timely parental awareness. The combined system demonstrates a practical and affordable IoT-based solution that strengthens transportation security, tracking, and communication in a school environment.

Figure 10: Implementation Design of the System

CONCLUSION

The proposed IoT-based school bus transportation system provides an efficient and secure solution for monitoring the student movement and bus location in real-time. By integrating RFID technology, GSM communication, GPS tracking, and servo-controlled access, the system ensures that only authorized the students can board the bus, while their parents are promptly notified through automated calls. The LCD and buzzer provide immediate visual and audio feedback for validation and security. Real-time location updates via GPS and ThingSpeak further enhance transparency and route management. The system significantly improves the safety and communication between school, students, and parents, while also reducing manual errors and response delays. Overall, the solution demonstrates the potential of IoT in transforming the traditional school transportation into a more intelligent, reliable, and student-centered service.

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